

Artifact of NaturalSym

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NaturalSym, proposed in *Natural Symbolic Execution-based Testing for Big Data Analytics (FSE24)*, is a symbolic execution-based tool to generate natural tests for big data analytics. Section 0 instructs the installation of our package. Section 1 guides users to run NaturalSym in a standalone mode. Section 2 details the replication of our evaluation.

0. Package Installation

We made our package available as a docker image so that users can simply run the following. Our package is also available at <https://github.com/UCLA-SEAL/NaturalSym>.

Get the package ready

Users can download our package from zenodo and build it yourself or directly pull it from docker hub (suggested).

```
> (download) https://zenodo.org/uploads/11090237
> docker build . -t thaddywu/naturalsym
or (suggested)
> docker image pull thaddywu/naturalsym
```

Start!

```
> docker run -it thaddywu/naturalsym /bin/bash
```

1. Run NaturalSym in a standard alone mode

Example

NaturalSym is a test generator for scala-based Apache Spark programs. To use NaturalSym, users need to provide a scala program under test and an input annotation file, e.g. *grades.scala* and *grades.config*.

- *grades.scala* contains a method `def execute(input1: RDD[String], input2: RDD[String])`, which takes two input tables respectively representing students' math and physics scores, and filters out students who fail the total score.
- *grades.config* contains user knowledge about the program input. Each line in *grades.config* corresponds to one input table in *grades.scala*, e.g. `input1 := Discrete("alice";"bob") | scipy.binom(100, 0.1)`.
The above annotation means that users give two examples of the first column (student name), i.e. "alice" and "bob".
The second column (maths score) should follow a binomial distribution `binom(n=100,p=0.1)`.

To run NaturalSym, try out `> ./naturalsym.sh grades.scala grades.config`. You'll see the generated tests both in console and *grades.tests*. The output snippet is shown below which refers to the test generated for the first condition that a student's math grade and physics grade can be found from two tables and the sum is smaller than 60.

```
Generated tests for Path1 in Rindir/1.smt2
[input1.csv]
alice,8
[input2.csv]
alice,34
```

Try it yourself!

Under the root folder, please execute `> ./naturalsym <target.scala> <target.config>`. You'll see the output in both console and `<target.tests>`.

- Limited by the back-end symbolic execution engine, the target method must be `execute` and input arguments must be of the shape `RDD[String]`. Please see our template in `template.scala`.
- The configuration file format is shown below. In general, each line of the configuration file declares user knowledge about each column from a input table delimited by "|". User knowledge can be none, an example list, Gaussian distribution, uniform distribution, or any distribution supported by Python scipy library.

```

<config>      := "" | <config> "\n" <tab>
<tab>         := <tab-name> ":" <cols>
<cols>       := "" | <cols> "|" <col>
<col>        := <none> | <examples> | <uniform> | <gaussian> | <trunc-gaussian> | <scipy-distr>
<none>       := ""
<examples>   := Discrete(<examples-delimited-by-comma>)
<uniform>    := Uniform(<l-bound>,<r-bound>)
<gaussian>   := Gaussian(<mu>,<sigma>)
<trunc-gaussian> := <l-bound><=Gaussian(<mu>,<sigma>)<=<r-bound>
<scipy-distr> := scipy.<distr-name>(<parameter-list>)

```

2. Replicate Evaluation of NaturalSym

To replicate our evaluation, we provide a streamlined script to complete all experiments: `> ./eval.sh`. This script contains three components: (1) run NaturalSym and every baseline, (2) collect all tests from each test generation tool, (3) run evaluation scripts. As it is extremely time-consuming to complete the entire evaluation cycle, we stored all intermediate files in our replication package. **If users are interested in running sub-parts of our evaluation (optional), we leave the details in below. To observe tests generated by different tools, users can find all tests in `./_aggregated_tests/`.**

Run NaturalSym `> ./NaturalSym/main.sh`

This command will run NaturalSym 5 times over 13 subject programs. As NaturalSym uses the same symbolic executor as BigTest [2], we produce BigTest's outputs in this script in order to save time. This script will also conduct the ablation study to evaluate the impact of statistical support in NaturalSym.

Time consumption is ~ 1 hour.

Run NaturalFuzz `> ./NaturalFuzz/main.sh`

This command will run NaturalFuzz [3] and its variants 5 times over 13 subject programs. NaturalFuzz is a fuzzer using original tests as seed (stored in `./_data/`) to create new tests. This script will also run NaturalFuzz-P using tests generated by BigTest as seed and NaturalFuzz-H using original tests and BigTest's tests as seed.

Time consumption is ~ 48 hours.

ChatGPT

All chat history with ChatGPT is contained in `./ChatGPT/chat-history.txt`

Run TestMiner `> ./TestMiner/main.sh`

This command will run TestMiner [1] and its variant TestMiner-DM+. TestMiner is a mining-based test generation tool. TestMiner-DM+ adopts additional big data tests (stored in `./_data/`) in its data mining stage.

Time consumption is ~ 5 minutes.

Figure 1: Our replication package contains 3 major components: (1) experiment scripts to run NaturalSym and multiple baselines, (2) a script to collect tests from all baselines, (3) evaluation scripts to run evaluation and produce tables and figures. Users can either run a streamlined script `./eval.sh` or run each script of each sub-component in order.

Test Aggregation > `python3 _aggregated_tests/main.py`

All tests using each test generation tool over 5 runs will be collected in this single folder.

For example, `_aggregated_tests/exp1/_naturalfuzz/airport/input1.csv` stores the input table 1 generated by NaturalFuzz on benchmark airport in the first run. In this folder, `_pure` stands for NaturalFuzz-P, `_hybrid` stands for NaturalFuzz-H, and `_testminer-retrained` stands for TestMiner-DM+.

Time consumption is ~ 1 min.

Evaluate Perplexity (Table 3) > `python3 Table3.Perplexity/main.py`

This script will evaluate test naturalness using perplexity on fine-tuned DistilGpt2 models. To re-train models, please execute: > `python3 Table3.Perplexity/train.py`.

`Table3.Perplexity/Table3.csv` contains the median perplexity of each tool and `Table3.Perplexity/Table3_extended.png` visualizes each tool's perplexity over each input table.

Time consumption is ~ 1 hour.

Evaluate Fault Detection Capability (Table 4) > `./Table4.FaultDetection/main.sh`

This script will count the number of injected bugs detected by each tool. `Table4.FaultDetection/Table4.csv` contains the #bugs found on each subject program.

Time consumption is ~ 1 hour.

Evaluate Path Coverage (Table 5) > `./Table5.PathCoverage/main.sh`

This script will count the number of program paths covered by each tool. `Table5.PathCoverage/main.sh` contains the #paths covered on each subject program.

Time consumption is ~ 1 hour.

User Study (Table 6) > `python3 Table6.UserStudy/main.py`

This script will collect the user study result in *Table6.UserStudy/Table6.csv*. User study 1 asks users to match shuffled column names with their values in tests generated by NaturalSym and BigTest. User study 2 asks users to mark their preference of tests between NaturalSym and BigTest.

To run the user study interface, users can run > `python3 -m http.server 8080` and open `http://0.0.0.0:8080/`.

In user study 1, users can drag each header element to the column with which they believe to match. In user study 2, tables generated by NaturalSym and BigTest are listed side by side and users can select tables to indicate their preference.

Compare Runtime Cost (Fig. 8) > `python3 Fig8.Runtime/main.py`

This script will collect the runtime statistics in *Fig8.Runtime/Fig8.png*.

Evaluate numerical outliers (Fig. 14) > `python3 Fig14.NumericalOutliers/main.py`

This script will draw the cumulative distribution of generated numeric values in *Fig14.NumericalOutliers/Fig14.png*.

References

- [1] Luca Della Toffola, Cristian-Alexandru Staicu, and Michael Pradel. Saying ‘hi!’ is not enough: Mining inputs for effective test generation. In 2017 32nd IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE), pages 44–49. IEEE, 2017.
- [2] Muhammad Ali Gulzar, Shaghayegh Mardani, Madanlal Musuvathi, and Miryung Kim. White-box testing of big data analytics with complex user-defined functions. In Proceedings of the 2019 27th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering, ESEC/FSE 2019, page 290–301, New York, NY, USA, 2019. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [3] Ahmad Humayun, Yaoxuan Wu, Miryung Kim, and Muhammad Ali Gulzar. Naturalfuzz: Natural input generation for big data analytics. In Proceedings of the 38th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering, San Francisco, CA, USA, 2023. Association for Computing Machinery.